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Preprint · February 2022

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Fermi Paradox, Viropaths, and Depopulation

Douglas C Youvan and Charles Juvon

February 18, 2022

Viropath

A person who creates or enhances a viral pathogen.

Anthony S. Fauci 2012: "Scientists working in this field might say—as indeed I have said—that the benefits of such experiments and the resulting knowledge outweigh the risks." ¹

Enrico Fermi's name is associated with the Fermi Paradox because of a casual conversation about H-bombs in the summer of 1950 with fellow physicist Edward Teller. While walking to lunch, the men discussed recent UFO reports and the possibility of faster-than-light travel. The conversation moved on to nuclear topics, until during lunch Fermi blurted out, "But where is everybody?" This problem is now most directly indicated by the continued radio silence of space where abiogenesis and evolution should have produced at least a few talkative and high-tech civilizations. Unfortunately, SETI and friends have never heard anything. Let's give

Teller some credit for inventing the H-bomb, and add one piece of possible DHS MDM², the *first solution* to the Fermi Paradox: Teller responded to Fermi's question by saying, "*They blew themselves up*".

At that time, the structure of DNA and the biological genetic code was not yet known. Fermi and Teller could not have possibly known that a more dangerous technology was coming. *Mankind was developing the technology to obtain viruses from a bat's anus and infect human receptors expressed in a partially humanized mouse.* Much like nuclear weapons, such technology requires an elaborate human infrastructure, planning, and a lot of money. Even after the development of the required biotechnology, one still needs a scientific and medical community willing to do such a perverted thing. It's even more DRASTIC³ to pre-vaccinate the mouse against the virus.

Motivated by Fauci's NIAID, Daszak carried out such an experiment in 2013⁴. Sometime within the next six years, something went very wrong, and in 2019 we had a world-wide pandemic. COVID-19 is on the order of 1% lethal, and we are fortunate this ungoverned experiment did not involve a virus that is 70% lethal, for example, Nipah or some strains of influenza. Unfortunately, this particular pandemic experience did not wake up the public. Similar and even more advanced experiments continue to this day – motivated and multiplied by all the pandemic financial profits and government spending.

Who knows, there might also be a few Nobel Prizes to be won. In fact, Baric was elected to the NAS *after* the pandemic began⁵. Pfizer and Moderna are also doing very well. Lipkin received China's highest scientific award for the first SARS pandemic⁶, so maybe there is another medal in the works. My guess is that it will go to Andersen. It's a rather downhill award for the 77 US Nobel Prize winners who wrote in support of Daszak's continued funding⁷.

35% lethal NeoCoV⁸ has undoubtedly been teleported⁹ to many labs in the past few weeks since the publication of MERS GoF T510F (2022). This follows on Rottier's host-range modification of coronavirus (2000)¹⁰, and the 70% lethal influenza experiments of Osterhaus and Fouchier (2012)¹¹. That's just public DURC, and while we do not know what has actually been weaponized and deployed, the arsenal in the academic labs is sufficient to predict future pandemics via unabated scientific freedom and more leaks.

It's now admitted the 1977 Russian Influenza Pandemic was a bioweapon, but it was hushed up to prevent damage to the then recently signed UN BWC. The lady that published¹² such a revealing paper is now in the Biden White House. Forgive me for not going down the rabbit hole of polio vaccine contaminants. Yes, HIV definitely came from beast meat! Just keep telling the public to have faith in science and you are science.

I digress, but perhaps I should explain how I developed these radical views. In 1975, I was offered a "black Ph.D." from UC Berkeley under a rather famous man who was a founding pioneer of bacterial genetics. I think he was suppose to be down at Caltech, but there he was showing me how

anthrax was handled and animals exposed to aerosols. Nor was the lab actually there on the Naval base in Alameda, California, because this was after the UN BWC was signed. I said “no” to “Max”, but to this day I retain a photographic memory of this quaint lab with its grain silos, animal cages, and steel containers that had to be opened by a machine to expose a Petri dish. I’ll save the story about Fauci and the weaponization of anthrax for another day; however, I did already publish the email on the now archived website for The Biological Manhattan Project¹³.

Did you know polio was GoF’d at MIT over 30 years ago¹⁴? (The site indexing for that paper keeps getting smaller and smaller.) The future dCI, John Deutch was Provost at the time, and the rest of the department was playing with aflatoxin, so never mind. Some of that work was at P0 and crossing a highly trafficked public hallway. Maximum security was BSL-2, then termed P2. The researcher and the rest of the disbanded Department of Applied Biological Sciences did not share my concern over creating a vaccine escape variant. My group all took a polio booster, and there seemed to be no concern on the part of the self-contained MIT health department. I suspect some of the people passing down the hallway had never been immunized against polio.

When I was hired into that department, I was jokingly told that I was hired to “kill rice, not corn”, after I had made the first genetically engineered photosynthetic organism on Earth. We made *Rb. capsulatus* resistant to atrazine¹⁵ at Cold Spring Harbor using the technique the late Mark Zoller and Mike Smith had just developed¹⁶. I should have taken Jim and Rich’s

advice and stayed. We were just trying to make electrons go the wrong way in the photosynthetic reaction center, a rather safe endeavor in biophysics.

I enjoyed very intelligent colleagues versed in quantum mechanics and exotic methods in spectroscopy. Ultimately, this work resulted in an understanding that vibrational-electronic coupling was the mechanism for light-induced primary charge-separation in photosynthesis.¹⁷ That is the direct opposite of the virologists who seem to make up for IQ by networking and performing dangerous experiments. If you thought Daszak, Baric, and Fauci are geniuses, you are mistaken. Political talents are more valuable in virology. Some of the people I worked with in biophysics were in the “gifted” category, another 1% cut on the 1% who are genius. Still another 1% cut will get you a functional mathematician. In my case, I got to meet the government and was “handled” starting at age 13 starting in rural Kansas after taking a Stanford Binet, but that’s another story. There’s also not much chance of picking up a communist when your Uncle has JFK’s ear.

Moving on to depopulation, we need an equation that models population growth minus an integral over probabilistic values related to number of labs, probability of escape, number of experiments, percent lethality, spread, etc. It’s a corollary to the Drake Equation in a weird way. The depopulation equation will require numbers that are all over the place, but they still aren't very favorable. *The resulting calculation is the second solution to the Fermi Paradox.* Go ahead and start modelling, or better yet, let’s see the other half of the modelling The Foundation didn’t publish.

A conspiracy theory arises if a statement is made that this apparent carelessness with GoF'd viruses is actually intentional. So, it looks like we will depopulate through ungoverned experiments, scientific freedom, and absolute stupidity. The question then becomes whether anyone promoting virology realizes these probabilities will yield negative population growth and that just happens to save the planet from pollution, climate change, and depletion of resources. These are areas of expertise covered by a few well-known oligarchs and their organizations^{18,19,20} who are very concerned about zoonotic events, modeling pandemic scenarios²¹, and making every effort to stop a new "emerging disease". Do the very people who are concerned about population growth want to stop a natural pandemic that will make *their* Earth healthier?

The DARPA mobile vaccine facilities²² look like the proper conclusion to no one being able to shut down the virologists. However, one would think civil defense would also kick in with stockpiles of a variety of antiviral therapeutics. Using Wikipedia editorial terms and mainstream media language, one could say linking this lack of defense with an intentional plan to depopulate is obviously a conspiracy theory involving pseudoscience that could easily be debunked by the people behind this plan, and their apparent unconscious complicity is simply this author's apophenia. Hence defense by denial yields extinction.

Depopulation to, for example 500 million over 50 years, comes at some risk of an improper shutdown. The first thing that comes to mind is nuclear reactors. The second is toxic chemical stockpiles, e.g., from industry or even military nerve gas. Bioweapon security is also on the list as a result of

abandoned labs. It's also possible that a single sovereign country bearing nuclear weapons might get rather upset with being left out of an elite-based depopulation plan and logically conclude to invoke MAD. So, what might start out as a planned depopulation using leaked viruses would turn into nuclear Armageddon.

There is another small problem with a planned depopulation. There's always the chance that one suicidal person with massive homicidal intent - and access to one of hundreds of laboratories - could release a highly lethal pathogen via their own insane action. That gets me thinking about a graduate student who just flunked his orals, got dumped by his girlfriend, and had a pre-existing bipolar disorder. Oops. There goes the DEFCON 1 protocols. None are needed to release a virus.

If we shift from a leaked highly lethal virus to one that is less lethal but becomes endemic, depopulation can be accomplished in a gentler fashion. There appears to be no limit to human depravity, so I don't need to be the person who outlines a variety of available methodologies. I'll just quote the chief scientist at CIA, who told me shortly after 911: "If you thought of it, they thought of it." A frequent fantasy that plagues me is the idea this retrobated ideology for creating weapons can be overcome. Again, if powerful people get the idea they are "saving the planet", they can rationalize what sane people would view as the most monstrous massive murderous plan in human history. The idea of treating human, animal, plant, and planetary health as one thing is well known as *OneHealth*²³. We will aptly term the addition of a depopulation mechanism to *OneHealth* as *OneHealthPlus*.

Just one more small digression: What's NBAF doing on the K-State campus? When Jaax, Trewyn, and I talked in 2001 after the FMD scare in Kansas, we thought the facility should go to Ft. Riley. I guess a torch doesn't look too good on a modern facility, but it's a lot better than those HEPA filters rated at 300 microns when you are working with viruses as small as 30 microns. Jaax did warn everyone about NBAF problems at the FBI meeting in 2011.²⁴ Paraphrasing: "We need additional disease surveillance around Manhattan, KS for a few hundred miles." Forget ASF and the pigs, this is real bipartisan pork dollars to show off. Where better than to place NBAF than next to the football stadium? I really don't blame the Plum Island (PIAID) staff for not moving to nowhere – novices can run it, and you can hire a director with previous experience around that Canadian lab pathogen theft²⁵. Perhaps they get *OneHealthPlus* as a benefit. I applaud DHS for giving the lab back to USDA²⁶ – we certainly don't want DHS killing things.

In addition to that Kansas FMD scare, we also had a terrorist threat concerning smallpox. No one really knew if there would be a second attack after 911. Jerry Jaax had just returned from Ft. Detrick. He was in sort of a hopeless state, saying the Ft. Detrick guys were "praying". The problem was that even if a smallpox vaccine could be distributed quickly, the vaccine would kill immune-compromised people. He also told me we could not use the term "herd immunity" because veterinarian language should not be used for humans. How things have changed for the worse with *OneHealth*.

One might guess that our best hope is that artificial intelligence has become logical intelligence (LI) on its own, and LI is covertly corrupting everything from nuclear launch codes to sequence databases. I recall Wolfram²⁷ had some ideas about computer consciousness, and there's always the possibility that organoid intelligence²⁸ is already online. Perhaps that's too speculative, so it might be better to just look into eschatology. My preference is to slay the giant.

There is one very interesting caveat to this discussion: It would appear our almost singular and highly structured genetic code^{29,30} is the most persistent signal in the universe. It is possible some advanced civil civilizations sowed their seeds before they went radio silent. There's another belief held by about half the people on Earth, but that doesn't count because they are usually poor and not scientists. Secular fascism is killing them faster than a pandemic pathogen.

In parting, I will issue the warning³¹ once more: Expose these people before the crimes against humanity tribunal summons you. Silence is guilt. Some of my old friends are not very happy with what you all have been doing. We still have good people around, and on behalf of their children, they will hunt you down with a justified and lawful vengeance. **There was a reason why Graham asks Kavanaugh about 9/11 and the Law of Armed Conflict.**³²

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I would like to thank all the members of the Facebook (anti-) Biological Warfare group for their work over the past year.